

success story

Empowering Data Exploration: EIFFEL Cognitive Search Engine Integration with GEOSS Platform Plus

Unlocking Climate Intelligence Through Collaborative Innovation

In a groundbreaking collaboration, the EIFFEL project has successfully integrated its Cognitive Search Engine developed by LIBRA AI into the GEOSS platform as a result of EIFFEL's successful collaboration with the GEOSS Platform Plus (GPP) project led by ESA. This milestone signifies a leap forward in Earth Observation, offering enhanced data exploration capabilities in the climate change domain.

The EIFFEL Cognitive Search Engine transcends the limitations of traditional search tools by leveraging advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques. By employing Natural Language Processing (NLP), the search engine goes beyond exact or fuzzy text matching, enabling semantic and conceptual understanding of user queries. Relying on a Large Language Model (LLM) and optimized for the Climate Change domain allows users to search for GEOSS Portal datasets more effectively compared to conventional keyword-based search. This breakthrough enhances the efficiency and accuracy of data retrieval, and thus significantly improving the accessibility of critical information in the GEOSS portal. It effectively fuses G. O. LLM-based cognitive search with the on demand filtering capabilities already established in GEOSS Platform to bring data discovery efficiency and user experience in a much higher level.

The integration of the EIFFEL Cognitive Search Engine with the GEOSS ecosystem through EIFFEL's collaboration with GPP project is a significant step towards empowering researchers and professionals of the EO Community with unprecedented access to relevant data and services. This capability it is expected to not only accelerating progress in climate change research but also facilitate the development of applications for informed decision-making towards the adoption of efficient climate adaption and mitigation strategies.

As EIFFEL continues to drive advancements in cognitive search technology, its collaboration with the GEOSS ecosystem sets a new standard for innovation in the field of Earth observation, ushering in a new era of informed decision-making for a sustainable future.

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

<https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/index.php/pilots>

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